

THE EFFECT OF VIRAL HEPATITIS B AND C INFECTION ON LABOR PRODUCTIVITY IN PAKISTAN; EVIDENCE FROM KHYBER PAKHTUNKHWA

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Abstract

Objective:

To estimate the effect of Viral hepatitis B and C infection on labor productivity in Pakistan

Data: primary data obtained from 2481 hepatitis B and C patients in 21 districts of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa from January 2023 to September 2023 from Viral hepatitis B and C through a well design questioner based on socio-economic indicator

Methodology: This study used descriptive statistical tools, Chi-Square test of statistical significance and OLS econometric techniques. Descriptive statistic was applied for demographic and social analysis of data, Chi-Square test of statistical significance was used to test association of viral hepatitis B and C with selected indicators whereas multiple regression econometric analysis was done for economic analysis of data.

Results: This study found direct association of viral hepatitis B and C with demographic and socioeconomic indicators included in the study. The statistic of chi-square, Pvalue of chi-square and P-values of Phi and Cramer's exhibited significant association of viral hepatitis B and C with Gender, Age, employment status, material status, geographical region, profession of patient, monthly income of patients and their family and time duration of treatment. The chi square and Pvalue of chi square and P-values of Phi and Cramer's Gender 10.973 (0.00), Age 51.28 (0.00), employment status, material status 20.33(0.00), geographical region 22.08 (0.00), profession of patient 314.38 (0.00), monthly income of patients and their family 73.45 (0.00) and time duration of treatment 189.080 (0.00) showed a significant direct association with hepatitis B and C. The

estimated results of OLS regression explored significant effect of Hepatitis B and C on absenteeism. The male patients have 22% more probability of being absent from their working place than female whereas on average patients age has indirect impact of viral hepatitis on labor productivity. Source of exposure and material status of the hepatitis patients were initiated indirect effect on absenteeism. The probability of absenteeism of married patients was estimated 25% less than unmarried patients. The OLS model estimates also showed significant direct association of absenteeism with the employment status hepatitis B and C. the probability of work impairment and absenteeism among self-employed, part time employee and retired persons found 55%, 52% and 97% respectively whereas the effect of dependent respondents and unemployed patients was found significantly indirect and estimated 8% and 17%. The probability of education, number of infected patients estimated direct medical cost and monthly income were found significant direct relation with absenteeism and estimated as 31% 41%, and 30% respectively.

INTRODUCTION

Chronic hepatitis B and C represent immense health and economic concerns globally and particularly in developing countries. These are the most predominant viral infections worldwide with about 248 million infected with viral hepatitis B and 271.1 million people with hepatitis C^[1]. The global premature deaths associated with hepatitis B in the last three decade were estimated approximately 580,500 to 800,000 whereas worldwide deaths from hepatitis C were approximately estimated to increase from 350,100 to 580,00 for during 1990 to 2017^[2]. Both hepatitis B and C spread by contaminated blood, sexual relation with infected person and use of contaminated instruments^[5], and this transfer can cause mortality and morbidity. The hepatitis B and Hepatitis C viruses are the causative mediators of HBV and HCV related disease^[3,4] and leads liver cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma and caused mortality and morbidity globally^[6,7].

The prevalence of hepatitis B and C occurred in developing and third world countries of the world. Pakistan secured the second most infected country where the occurrence of viral hepatitis B and C are approximately 2.6% and 5% respectively after Egypt^[8]. Every 40th and 20th person in Pakistan are infected with hepatitis B and C virus^[8]. As a low-income country Pakistan faced sever healthcare problems that caused productivity to fall, cut in income affect savings and rise poverty in the

country, it also caused, morbidity and mortality rate to rise because of premature deaths. Developing countries like Pakistan the key factors of viral transmission are use of contaminated medical equipment's, dental clinics, Barber shop, beauty parlor, sexual relation with infected persons, unhealthy sewerage system and vertical transmission^[8].

In the financial year 2005, Pakistan's national income declined by 1 billion dollars because of premature deaths associated with chronic disease (WHO report- facing the facts). In the United States of America only hepatitis C imposed economic burden of \$ 10 billion per years. The cost of the disease consists of direct medical cost and indirect medical costs. Direct medical cost includes expenses incurred for diagnostic and medication whereas indirect comprises traveling expenses, special diet expenses, loss of productivity, morbidity, loss of productivity due to premature deaths and cut in foreign remittance.

Hepatitis B and C both adversely affect labor productivity in form of absenteeism and presentism. Sajjad and Nosheen (2022) found significant effect of hepatitis on labor productivity in terms of absenteeism and presentism that estimated an average per patient and their attendant's absenteeism and presentism 1.89 days per month and total working days lost in Pakistan were estimated 32,432,400. Furthermore, hepatitis B and C had also

found significant indirect impact on labor mobility employment and mortality and concluded that 2.07% visa rejection, 6.2% job rejection, 1.2% job termination and 5.2% morality caused by hepatitis B and C. similarly the effect of hepatitis B and C was found indirect and caused decline in income in term of loss of working days and sell of assents. In Iran productivity loss associated with hepatitis B and C were estimated 23.7% and 13% and concluded that workers with hepatitis C infection earn less than healthy worker and estimated. Younossi et al (2016). in the United Kingdom economic loss of viral Hepatitis were calculated as 23.8 % activity impairment, 6.7 % productivity loss due to absenteeism and 21.3% occurred because hepatitis presenteeism (Jie Kie Phang et al (2020). The annual output loss per worker estimated in the United States of America was 8352 dollar per worker Jun Su et al (2010).

Similarly, the uncontrolled prevalence of viral hepatitis B and C caused productivity to fall and mortality to rise. Morbidity and mortality triggered to Hepatitis B and C also affect the socioeconomic indicators that will evidently increases in the next decade in the world and especially in Pakistan. The current study aims to examine the effect of viral hepatitis B and C on labor productivity in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan.

Objective of the study

To the best of authors knowledge, there is no study conducted in Pakistan to estimate the economic assessment of Hepatitis B and C by estimation of work productivity loss. Considering the increasing trend in the prevalence of viral hepatitis a comprehensive economic analysis was necessary to conduct a study and analyze the economic aspect of viral hepatitis B and C in Pakistan.

Data and Methodology

Demographic analysis of data:

Table 1. Gender wise distribution of the patient with respective district

		Female	Male	
District of the Patient	Malakand	41	51	92

This is an analytical study conducted in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa in 2023 on Hepatitis B and C patients in different districts.

Data: primary data obtained from 2481 hepatitis B and C patients in 21 districts of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa in January 2023 to September 2023. Viral hepatitis B and C patients visited to District headquarter hospital (D.H.Q), private hospitals and doctor’s clinic from treatment. Total of about 10,000 patients were contacted and data based on socio-economic indicator was obtained from every 5th hepatitis C and third Hepatitis B patients.

Methodology: This study used descriptive statistical tools, Chi-Square test of statistical significance and OLS econometric techniques. Descriptive statistic was applied for demographic and social analysis of data, Chi-Square test of statistical significance was used to test association of viral hepatitis B and C with selected indicators whereas multiple regression econometric analysis was done for economic analysis of data.

Econometric model: Absenteeism (work loss/day) during infection or treatment

$$\text{Absenteeism} = b_0 + b_1 (\text{Gender}) + b_2 (\text{Age}) + b_3 (\text{monthly income}) + b_4 (\text{education}) + b_5 (\text{employment status}) + b_6 (\text{insurance status}) + b_7 (\text{number of visits to hospital}) + b_8 (\text{source of exposure}) + e$$

In the equation, dependent variable signposts the absenteeism patients during the treatment by the exposed to the hepatitis. As the dependent variable is a continuous variable, thus the Equation is estimated by Ordinary Least Square (OLS) methodology.

Data analysis, Results and discussion

Statistical analysis; SPSS software (version 16) were used for Descriptive analysis of data. The data was presented in percentage, mean and range.

	Lower Dir	46	54	100
	Upper Dir	34	65	99
	Swat	40	60	100
	Bunner	44	56	100
	Bajaur	24	76	100
	Mardan	36	64	100
	Shangla	40	60	100
	Bannu	41	51	92
	Charsada	49	50	99
	D-I-Khan	44	56	100
	Hango	55	45	100
	Kohat	58	42	100
	Mansehra	80	120	200
	Nowshehra	80	120	200
	Peshawar	51	199	250
	Swabi	51	48	99
	Abbottabad	80	120	200
	Waziristan	20	30	50
	Lakki Marwat	60	40	100
	Haripur	30	70	100

Total	996	1485	2481
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Table 1 explored the gender and district wise representation of data. Data was obtained from 21 districts of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. 1485 respondents were male and 996 respondents were female. In all districts the ratio of male respondents was higher

except Hango, Kohat and Lakki Marwat where female respondents were more than male. In overall 40.14% of the respondents were female and 59.86% were male.

Table 2: Age wise distribution of the data

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	5-18 Years	76	3.1	3.1	3.1
	19-32 Years	829	33.4	33.4	36.5
	33-46 Years	792	31.9	31.9	68.4
	47-60 Years	496	20.0	20.0	88.4
	>60 Years	289	11.6	11.6	100.0
	Total	2482	100.0	100.0	

Table 2 indicated the number of respondents from a particular age. The data was analyzed for patients aged 5 to 70 years. The above table shows that 85.3 % patients are from working age population

whereas 3.1 % patients are minors and 11.6% patients aged above 60 years that is retainment age in Pakistan

Table 3: Marital status of the respondent

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Married	1967	79.3	79.3	79.3
	un married	513	20.7	20.7	99.9
	Total	2482	100.0	100.0	

Table 4: Education and Awareness

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	No	794	32.0	32.0	32.0
	Primary	537	21.6	21.6	53.6
	High School	693	27.9	27.9	81.5
	Collage/University	458	18.5	18.5	100.0
	Total	2482	100.0	100.0	

Table 3 and Table 4 the material status and education and awareness of the patients. In total 1967 (79.3 %) of the respondents were married and 513 (20.7%) are unmarried whereas the education of 794 (32.0%), 537 (21.5), 693 (27.9%) and 458

(18.5%) of the patients uneducated, primary education, high school and college or university. That indicates high prevalence of hepatitis B and C among uneducated and low education people

Table 4: Profession of the patient

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
	Labor	321	12.9	12.9	12.9
	House Wife	849	34.2	34.2	47.9
	Students	406	16.4	16.4	64.2
	Teacher	121	4.9	4.9	69.1
	Tailor	39	1.6	1.6	70.7
	Army	21	.8	.8	71.5
	Driver	67	2.7	2.7	74.2
	property dealer	3	.001	.001	74.3

Doctor	3	.001	.001	74.5
Former	323	13.0	13.0	87.5
Jeweler	15	.6	.6	88.1
shopkeeper	129	5.2	5.2	93.3
security guard	3	.1	.1	93.4
govt job	43	1.7	1.7	95.1
bank employee	35	1.4	1.4	96.5
Own business	38	1.5	1.5	98.1
Lawyer	12	.5	.5	98.5
Unemployed	50	1.9	1.9	99.8
Private Job	4	.2	.2	100.0
Total	2482	100.0	100.0	

The profession of respondent was displayed in table 4 of the current study. The table shows that about 48.8% of the respondents are unemployed (house wife 849 plus unemployed male 50), 16.4% of Hepatitis patients are students, 12.9% are teachers,

1.9 % are government employees whereas the remaining 23% are self-employed in form of labor, security guard, jeweler, private job, shopkeeper, driver etc.

Table 5: Monthly Income of the patient

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	<10000	50	2.0	2.0	2.0
	10001-20000	1283	51.7	51.7	53.7
	20001-30000	797	32.1	32.1	85.8

	30001-40000	289	11.6	11.6	97.5
	>40000	62	2.5	2.5	100.0
	Total	2482	100.0	100.0	

Monthly income of the patients and their family are displayed in table 5 that explains that about 54% of patient's family income fall below 20,000 per whereas the minimum wage in Pakistan are fixed at 18,000 per month, 43% patients fall in the middle class and there family income lies in 20,000 to 40,000 whereas 2.5% patients belongs to patients with family income of more than 40,000 .

The above table also explains that the incidence of viral hepatitis occurs more in poor people while the middle- and upper-class population were less affected by viral hepatitis. Rich people regularly visited to doctor's clinic and their disease are diagnosis at early stage and treated so the burden of disease fall less on these peoples.

Table 6: Number of days spent at each visit at hospital/ Doctor's clinic

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	few hours	521	21.0	21.0	21.0
	one day	1863	75.1	75.1	96.1
	one week	76	3.1	3.1	99.1
	Others	22	.9	.9	100.0
	Total	2482	100.0	100.0	

Leve days from work due to hepatitis B and C in the course of treatment were highlighted in the above table 6. The table states that 75.1% of the patients and their caregiver reported full day off from their work to visit hospital/ doctor clinic for treatment,

21% reported few hours or partial leave from work 76 (3.1%) patients recorded one week leave to visit hospital/ doctor clinic. That shows direct relation of work impairment and hepatitis B and C

Table 7: Time Duration of Treatment

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent

Valid	one month	227	9.1	9.1	9.1
	3 months	253	10.2	10.2	19.3
	6 months	802	32.3	32.3	51.7
	>6 months	1200	48.3	48.3	100.0
	Total	2482	100.0	100.0	

Table 7 shows the time duration of each patient treatment. 227 (9.1%) patients are those who just started their treatment, 10.2% patients reported 3 months treatment whereas 802 (32.3%) and 1200 (48.3%) patients 6 months and more than 6

months' time duration for diagnostic and treatment of Viral hepatitis B and C. that explained that Hepatitis B and C are long lasting disease and effect health and income adversely.

Table 8: Chi square test for association of viral hepatitis with socio-economic indicators

Chi square test results table

	Pearson Square	Chi-Square	Significance P-value	Phi	Significance P-value	Cramer's V	Significance P-value
Gender of the Patient	10.973		0.00	0.028	0.00	0.028	0.00
Age of the Patient	51.28		0.00	0.144	0.00	0.102	0.00
Marital status	20.33		0.00	0.090	0.00	0.064	0.00

Geographical Regions	22.08	0.00	0072	0.00	0.068	0.00
Profession	314.385	0.00	0.356	0.00	0.252	0.00
Monthly Income	73.450	0.00	0.172	0.00	0.122	0.00
Time Duration of Treatment	189.080	0.00	0.276	0.00	0.195	0.00

Table 8 of this study expressed the association of viral hepatitis B and C with demographic and socio-economic indicators included in the study. The statistic of chi-square, P-value of chi-square and P-values of Phi and Cramer's exhibited significant association of viral hepatitis Band C with Gender, Age, employment status, material status, geographical region, profession of patient, monthly income of patients and their family and time duration of treatment. The chi square and Pvalue of

chi square and P- values of Phi and Cramer's Gender 10.973 (0.00), Age51.28 (0.00), employment status, material status 20.33(0.00), geographical region 22.08 (0.00), profession of patient 314.38 (0.00), monthly income of patients and their family 73.45 (0.00) and time duration of treatment 189.080 (0.00) sowed a significant direct association with hepatitis B and C that explain hepatitis B and C directly affect these indicator @ 5% level of significance.

Table 10: Baseline estimation Absenteeism during treatment of viral hepatitis B and C patients and their caregivers

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5	Model 6	Model 7	Model 8	Model 9	Model 10
Male	0.021 (0.015)	0.023 (0.014)	0.022 (0.014)	0.020 (0.014)	0.020 (0.014)	0.018 (0.014)	0.019 (0.014)	0.022 (0.014)	0.022 (0.014)	0.22 (0.013)
Age of the Patient	0.014* (0.008)	0.011 (0.008)	0.011 (0.008)	0.011 (0.008)	0.010 (0.008)	0.011 (0.008)	0.010 (0.008)	0.008 (0.008)	0.007 (0.008)	-0.03 (0.008)

Married	-0.031*	-0.028	-0.029	-0.029	-0.027	-0.024	-0.025	-0.018	-0.022	-0.05
	(0.019)	(0.019)	(0.018)	(0.018)	(0.018)	(0.018)	(0.018)	(0.018)	(0.018)	(0.017)
Dental clinic	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-0.037
	0.102**	0.089*	0.092**	0.092**	0.090**	0.090**	0.089**	0.077**	0.079**	
	*	**	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	
	(0.028)	(0.028)	(0.028)	(0.028)	(0.028)	(0.028)	(0.028)	(0.028)	(0.028)	(0.027)
Sexual relation	0.136**	0.137*	0.137*	0.137**	0.152**	0.141**	0.155**	0.139**	0.154**	0.179**
	*	**	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
	(0.050)	(0.051)	(0.050)	(0.050)	(0.051)	(0.053)	(0.057)	(0.056)	(0.055)	(0.055)
Barber shop	0.101**	0.108*	0.117*	0.128**	0.130**	0.119**	0.115**	0.085**	0.088**	0.80**
	*	**	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	
	(0.020)	(0.021)	(0.021)	(0.022)	(0.024)	(0.024)	(0.024)	(0.022)	(0.023)	(0.033)
Beauty parlour	-0.024	-0.017	-0.026	-0.019	-0.022	-0.026	-0.021	0.019	0.022	0.30
Surgery	(0.068)	(0.067)	(-0.068)	(-0.068)	(-0.068)	(-0.067)	(-0.066)	(-0.067)	(0.065)	(-0.66)
Blood transfusion	-0.074*	0.062	0.063	0.056	0.054	0.055	0.061	-0.051	0.047	0.035
Vertical transmission	(0.040)	(0.040)	(0.040)	(0.040)	(0.040)	(0.040)	(0.041)	(0.041)	(0.042)	(0.040)
Part time employee <30 hr/week	-0.110	-0.107	-0.117*	-0.114	-0.113	-0.103	-0.107	-0.099	-0.099	-0.40
Selfemployee	(0.069)	(0.070)	(0.071)	(0.071)	(0.071)	(0.066)	(0.066)	(0.064)	(0.064)	(0.061)
Dependent	0.082**	0.078*	0.052**	0.053**	0.055**	0.052**	0.046**	0.035*	0.036*	0.06
Retired	(0.019)	**	(0.021)	(0.021)	(0.021)	(0.021)	(0.021)	(0.021)	(0.021)	(0.021)
	0.206**	(0.019)	0.214**	0.210**	0.203**	0.178**	0.175**	0.200**	0.221**	0.202**
	*	0.215*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
	(0.052)	**	(0.046)	(0.045)	(0.045)	(0.045)	(0.046)	(0.051)	(0.051)	(0.052)
	0.087**	(0.054)	0.083**	0.084**	0.062**	0.056*	0.057**	0.048*	0.077**	0.55*
	(0.027)	0.079*	(0.028)	(0.028)	(0.029)	(-0.029)	(-0.029)	(-0.029)	(0.030)	(0.030)
	0.017	**	0.013	0.013	0.011	0.017	0.014	-0.025	0.003	-0.17
	(0.026)	(0.027)	(0.027)	(0.027)	(0.029)	(0.029)	(0.029)	(0.029)	(0.028)	(0.028)
	0.104**	0.010	0.081**	0.105**	0.073**	0.063*	0.064*	0.079**	0.071*	0.97**
	*	(0.027)	(0.033)	*	(0.036)	(0.036)	(0.035)	(0.037)	(0.041)	(0.041)
	(0.028)	0.090*		(0.033)						
		**								
		(0.030)								
un-employed	-0.078	-0.082	-0.088	-0.065	-0.089	-0.076	-0.092	-0.124	-0.096	0.08
	(0.098)	(0.099)	(0.094)	(0.096)	(0.096)	(0.099)	(0.099)	(0.102)	(0.103)	(0.094)
Education and	0.045**	0.045*	0.046**	0.046**	0.046**	0.048**	0.046**	0.040**	0.034**	0.20***

Total Cost Spent on Treatment Monthly Income	-	-	-0.07	0.061**	0.066**	(0.015)	*	*	0.30***	(0.014)	(0.014)	0.037**	*	(0.011)	(0.011)	0.94***	(0.010)
Total Cost of Visit Per Month	1.725**	1.650*	1.604**	1.602**	1.632**	1.772**	1.688**	1.818**	1.754**	1.587**							
Constant	*	**	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*							
	(0.050)	(0.058)	(0.057)	(0.057)	(0.057)	(0.058)	(0.074)	(0.081)	(0.084)	(0.084)							
Observations	2482	2482	2482	2482	2482	2482	2482	2482	2482	2482	2482	2482	2482	2482	2482	2482	2482

Notes: This table presents the results of OLS regressions examining the effects of hepatitis on labor productivity. Standard errors (in brackets) are robust to arbitrary heteroskedasticity. *, **, and *** indicate statistical significance at the 10%, 5% and 1% level, respectively. The estimated results of OLS regression model emphasized in table 10. The above table highlighted the consequence of Viral Hepatitis B and C on absenteeism patients age, patients' gender, material status, employment status of the patient, source of exposure, family size of the infected person, monthly income, number of infected persons with hepatitis B or C, sale of assets, direct and indirect cost, number of visits per month to doctors clinic and geographical region. In the above table 10 explored significant effect of Hepatitis B and C on absenteeism. The magnitude of male patients 0.022 with p-value of 0.013 model 10 explains that male patients has 22% more probability of being absent from their working place than female whereas on average patients age has indirect impact of viral hepatitis on labor productivity while in model 7,8, and 9 the impact is direct. Source of exposure and material status of the hepatitis B and C patients were initiated indirect effect on absenteeism. The probability of absenteeism of

married patients was estimated 25% less than unmarried patients while the influence of dental clinic, blood transfusion and surgery were found indirect. On the other side patients infected with viral hepatitis B and C from Barber shop, beauty parlor, sexual relations, and vertical transmission has found significantly direct relation of hepatitis B and C with work impairment (absenteeism). The OLS model estimates also showed significant direct association of absenteeism with the employment status hepatitis B and C. the probability of work impairment and absenteeism among self-employed, part time employee and retired persons found 55%, 52% and 97% respectively whereas the effect of dependent respondents and unemployed patients was found significantly indirect and estimated 8% and 17%. The probability of education, number of infected patients estimated direct medical cost and monthly income were found significant direct relation with absenteeism and estimated as 31% 41%, and 30% respectively. Model 10 also explored that health insurance estimated direct medical cost and total number of family member indirect probability hepatitis B and C of being absent from work during the course of treatment.

Conclusion and discussion

Chronic hepatitis B and C represents huge health and economic concerns globally and particularly in developing countries. These are the most predominant viral infections worldwide with about 248 million infected with viral hepatitis B and 271.1 million people with hepatitis C. The global premature deaths associated with hepatitis B in the last three decades were estimated approximately 580,500 to 800,000 whereas worldwide deaths from hepatitis C were approximately estimated to increase from 350,100 to 580,000 for during 1990 to 2017. Both hepatitis B and C spread by contaminated blood, sexual relation with infected person and use of contaminated instruments^[5], and this transfer can cause mortality and morbidity. The hepatitis B and Hepatitis C viruses are the

causative mediators of HBV and HCV related disease^[3,4] and leads liver cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma and caused mortality and morbidity globally. This study aims to estimate the effect of Viral hepatitis B and C infection on labor productivity in Pakistan. Primary data obtained from 2481 hepatitis B and C patients in 21 districts of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa from January 2023 to September 2023 from Viral hepatitis B and C through a well design questionnaire based on socio-economic indicator. Descriptive statistical tools, Chi-Square test of statistical significance and OLS econometric techniques were used for data analysis. Descriptive statistic was applied for demographic and social analysis of data, Chi-Square test of statistical significance was used to test association of viral hepatitis B and C with selected indicators whereas multiple regression econometric analysis was done for economic analysis of data.

This study also found direct association of viral hepatitis B and C with demographic and socioeconomic indicators included in the study. The statistic of chi-square, P-value of chi-square and P-values of Phi and Cramer's exhibited significant association of viral hepatitis B and C with Gender, Age, employment status, material status, geographical region, profession of patient, monthly income of patients and their family and time duration of treatment. The chi square and Pvalue of chi square and P-values of Phi and Cramer's Gender 10.973 (0.00), Age 51.28 (0.00), employment status, material status 20.33(0.00), geographical region 22.08 (0.00), profession of patient 314.38 (0.00), monthly income of patients and their family 73.45 (0.00) and

time duration of treatment 189.080 (0.00) showed a significant direct association with hepatitis B and C. The estimated results of OLS regression explored significant effect of Hepatitis B and C on absenteeism. The male patients have 22% more probability of being absent from their working place than female whereas on average patients age has indirect impact of viral hepatitis on labor productivity. Source of exposure and material status of the hepatitis patients were initiated indirect effect on absenteeism. The probability of absenteeism of married patients was estimated 25% less than unmarried patients. The OLS model estimates also showed significant direct association of absenteeism with the employment status hepatitis B and C. The probability of work impairment and absenteeism among self-employed, part time employee and retired persons found 55%, 52% and 97% respectively whereas the effect of dependent respondents and unemployed patients was found significantly indirect and estimated 8% and 17%. The probability of education, number of infected patients estimated direct medical cost and monthly income were found significant direct relation with absenteeism and estimated as 31% 41%, and 30% respectively.

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